

Mercury Complexes of Compounds containing Amino Group

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Some of the compounds containing amino group have been cyanoethylated using Triton B as a catalyst in presence of glacial acetic acid to obtain propionitrile derivative. The complexes of these compounds have been prepared with mercuric chloride. The quantitative estimation of mercury, infrared spectroscopy, microanalysis and conductance measurements in nitrobenzene showed that the metal-ligand ratio is 1 : 2 and the complexes are of non-electrolyte type having general formula HgL_2Cl_2 , where L = ligand.

MANY mercury complexes prepared from organic ligands are used as insecticides^{1,2}, fungicide³, inflammatory agents⁴, disinfectants⁵. So we have tried to synthesise mercury complexes with α -naphthylamine, β -naphthylamine, β -(1-naphthylamino)propionitrile, 4,4'-(biaminobiphenyl), β, β' -(4,4'-biaminobiphenyl)propionitrile in order to find out if they can be used for any biological purpose.

Mercury forms direct covalent as well as coordinate links with nitrogen. Coordination of one mole of mercuric salt and two moles of a high molecular weight amine has been shown to yield a complex having a 2 : 1 ratio with respect to amine and metal⁶. Similarly a number of complexes have been reported by Tanner⁷ using higher aliphatic amines with mercuric chloride. Binding of mercury(II) by a variety of heterocyclic and aromatic nitrogen ligands has also been reported^{8,9}. The present paper reports studies on the complexes of mercury(II) with α -naphthylamine, β -naphthylamine, β -(1-naphthylamino)propionitrile, 4,4'-(biaminobiphenyl) and β, β' -(4,4'-biaminobiphenyl)propionitrile.

Experimental

Acrylonitrile was purified by distillation. All other chemicals were of B.D.H. reagent grade.

Preparation of ligands :

β -(1-Naphthylamino)propionitrile : A mixture of α -naphthylamine (7 g, 0.05 mol), acrylonitrile (0.7 ml, 0.06 mol) and glacial acetic acid (2.5 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 24 h. The product obtained was extracted with chloroform, washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After filtration and evaporating the solvent, cyanoethyl derivative obtained was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 125°.

β, β' -(4,4'-Biaminobiphenyl)propionitrile : A mixture of 4,4'-(biaminobiphenyl) (5 g, 0.03 mol), acrylonitrile (2.5 ml, 0.04 mol) and glacial acetic acid (3 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 20 h. A solution of the product in ethylene dichloride was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Evaporation of the solvent yielded a cyanoethyl derivative which was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 120-121°.

Preparation of complexes : Complexes were prepared by refluxing a solution of mercuric chloride in ethanol with a solution of α -naphthylamine, β -naphthylamine, β -(1-naphthylamino)propionitrile, 4,4'-(biaminobiphenyl) or β, β' -(4,4'-biaminobiphenyl)propionitrile in ethanol in 1 : 2 molar ratio for 8-10 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, filtered and dried in vacuum for 2 h. The complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents, viz. benzene, dioxan, chloroform, methanol and tetrahydrofuran. However, at very high dilution they are soluble in nitrobenzene.

Analyses and measurements : The metal and chloride contents were determined by standard methods¹⁰.

Conductivity measurements were carried out at 25° with CM-82T instrument, cell constant of 1.0. The complexes were dissolved in nitrobenzene for such measurements. The results are presented in the Table 1. Ir spectra were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer 137E spectrophotometer. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out using Gouy method and $HgCo(SCN)_4$ as calibrant.

Results and Discussion

Analytical results indicate that the metal ligand ratio is 1 : 2 and may be represented as ML_2Cl_2 , where M is metal and L is ligand. The molar

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND CONDUCTIVITY DATA OF THE MERCURY(II) COMPLEXES*

Complex	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					Conductance $\times 10^{-3} \Omega^{-1}$
	M	C	H	N	Cl	
Dichloro-bis-(β -naphthylamine)mercury	36.18 (35.98)	43.26 (43.05)	3.47 (3.23)	5.29 (5.02)	12.94 (12.72)	0.82
Dichloro-bis-(α -naphthylamine)mercury	35.79 (35.98)	43.34 (43.05)	3.48 (3.23)	5.28 (5.02)	12.52 (12.72)	0.96
Dichloro-bis- β -(1-naphthylamino)propionitrile mercury	30.03 (30.23)	47.22 (47.02)	3.85 (3.62)	8.65 (8.44)	10.98 (10.69)	1.24
Dichloro-bis- β, β' -(4,4'-biaminobiphenyl)mercury	31.58 (31.37)	45.29 (45.03)	3.97 (3.75)	8.98 (8.76)	11.29 (11.09)	0.76
Dichloro-bis- β, β' -(4,4'-biaminobiphenyl)propionitrile mercury	24.04 (23.84)	51.55 (51.34)	3.29 (3.09)	13.52 (13.31)	8.17 (8.43)	1.12

* All the complexes were found to be diamagnetic.

conductance of complexes were recorded in nitrobenzene at the concentration of $1 \mu M$ which showed the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes¹¹. The nature of the complex showed that the halogen atoms are also bonded to the metal coordination sphere.

Infrared spectra of these complexes show two strong bands at $3000-3500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which accounts for NH_2 stretching vibration. These bands occur at frequencies about $60-100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ lower than those of the parent compound. Thus weakening of the NH_2 bands, presumably due to the drainage of electrons from the nitrogen atom towards metal, indicates that these complexes exist as coordination compounds. The other band is observed at $1500-1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to bending vibration of NH_2 group. This band is also shifted to lower frequency region on coordination with metal chloride. $\text{C}=\text{N}$ stretching frequency for each of these derivatives, observed around $2210-2260 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, shifted to lower frequency. This is presumably due to the coordination of the cyano group to the metal. All the mercury(II)

complexes have been found to be diamagnetic, suggesting tetrahedral/octahedral geometry.

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